

The Historical Toponyms of the Events of Arrival in the Oasis of Ferghana

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Abstract:

this article, the historical processes of the game in the Ferghana valley, the introduction of nomadic players from the northern and northern urban areas of Central Asia, the history of the maturation of toponym accessories are shown in detail.

Keywords: valley, wound, region, mountain, resettlement, farming, settlement wounds, toponyms, middle Ages, culture, culture.

Introduction. The radic of settlement of the situation in Ferghana valley go back to the very modern times, and such processes have been going on for a long time and each stage of history has its own way. That is, the number of shelters in the valley increased as a result of various conflicts between the aid and assortment cabinets in the early Middle Ages.

Part. In this case, on the one hand, the arrival of various nomadic peoples from the northern and northeastern-eastern regions of Central Asia was expected, and on the other hand, the regions of the main - directly and directly location in parts.

Before analyzing the emergence of historical toponyms in the Ferghana valley in the late middle Ages, it is necessary to briefly familiarize with the characteristics of toponyms in the region, their similarities and differences with place names in other regions. The first toponyms of the Ferghana valley date back to the last quarter of the last millennium BC, and they are mainly recorded in ancient Chinese chronicles and Greek sources. The oldest name of the valley – “Parkana” is found in Greek sources in IV-III centuries BC, while this place is mentioned in Chinese chronicles under the name “Da-yuan” [1]. Also, as one of the major settlements in the valley, the toponym “Ershi” was mentioned in ancient Chinese chronicles, and researchers have not yet reached a consensus on the local form of this term.

The early middle ages and later periods are considered to be the period when many settlements began to appear in the Ferghana valley. During this period, the general name of the valley – “Ferghana” appears in Chinese chronicles as “Bakhan”, “Polonna”, “Bochanna”, “Nin-yuan” [2], “Ferghana” in written sources in Arabic and Persian [3], “Fraganic” is found in the Mugh mountain Sugdian documents, and “Ferghan” is found in coins with Sugdian writing [4].

Akhsikent, one of the major settlements of the valley, is mentioned in the Chinese chronicles as “Sigyan”, Guva – “Humin”, Koson - Kuishuan or Gesai, Uzgand - Yuchen [5]. Also, in the Arabic-Persian language sources, together with the toponyms of Koson, Uzgand, the forms of Akhsikent, Akhsikat, and Qubo are found, in addition to these place names, Isfara, Karvonbast, Urast, Khurshab, Andigon, Sokh, Osh, Jadgal (Chatqal), Bob (Pop), Settlements such as Khukand, Khaylam, Miyonrud as the names of cities, towns and large villages of the valley is mentioned [6].

By the Middle Ages, the names of the Ferghana valley appeared in Turkish sources, in addition to written sources in Chinese, Arabic and Persian languages. Names of places in the valley are found for the first time in Makhmud Koshgari’s “Devonu Lugotit-Turk” in the forms Ferghana, Uzgand - Uzkend, and in “Boburnoma” Turkish toponyms in the valley such as “Between two waters” (Between Norin and Karadarya) are mentioned [7].

When the increase in the number of Turkic toponyms in the Ferghana valley took on a serious tone in the middle ages and reached its last stage, the number of Turkic place names - ethnonyms and patronymics in the region became extensive. In the middle ages, Turkish and Turko-Mongol clans settled in the valley, and in the last middle ages, mainly Uzbek and Kyrgyz clans, and partly Karakalpak, Uyghur and Kazakhs founded their settlements. Especially during the Shaibani state and the Kokan Khanate, several dozen Uzbek villages with a nomadic base rose up in the valley. Also, in the mountainous and sub-mountainous regions of the valley, several tens of ovuls related to Kyrgyz clans appear. In addition, it is understood that some of the settlements in the valley are place names related to Mongolian clans, and their formation period corresponds to the period of the nomadic Uzbek and Kyrgyz clans, or a little earlier - to the era of the Chigatai dynasty and the Timurids.

Some of the toponyms of the Ferghana valley, which make up the oldest layer of toponyms, were recorded in the written sources of their time, and some of them have survived to this day. Toponyms of Parkana or Ferghana are one of the most convincing examples of this, and place names such as Asaka, Kuva, Oval, Varzik are place names that have not yet been determined to which language group they belong and have given rise to several hypotheses. The question of whether the language of the ancient Ferghanas, spoken from the last millennium BC to the last quarter of the millennium AD, belongs to the Iranian language group of the Indo-European languages or to the Turkic group of the Altaic language family, or to another language group, has not yet been resolved.

It is known that the land population of the Ferghana Valley was mostly settled farmers and lived in cities and villages, while the majority of nomadic herders were in the mountain and sub-mountain regions of the region. Despite the fact that Ferghana is bordered by Eastern Iranian and Turkic peoples such as Choch, Isjifob (Cayram), Tarozi, Talas, Koshghar, Tokharistan, and Ustrushona on four sides, Ferghana people have their own spoken language. known from the records of the monk Xuan Tsang (629–645).

Conclusion. This monk, who passed through Ettisuv, Sayram, Choch, and Sughd, neighboring countries to the north-west of Ferghana, noted that most of the inhabitants of the mentioned countries speak Suli (Sugdian) and said that the language [of the people of Fei-han] is different from that of other countries emphasizes that it is not similar to the language of any surrounding country.

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